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REAL TIME FACE FEATURE EXTRACTION AND RECOGNITION USING ROBUST ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT:

Human face detection and recognition play important roles in many applications such as video surveillance and face image database management. In our project, we have studied worked on both face recognition and detection techniques and developed algorithms for them. In face recognition the algorithm used is Robust in which we recognize an unknown test image by comparing it with the known training images stored in the database as well as give information regarding the person recognized. These techniques works well under robust conditions like complex background, different face positions. These algorithms give different rates of accuracy under different conditions as experimentally observed.

In face detection, we have developed an algorithm that can detect human faces from an image. We have taken skin colour as a tool for detection. This technique works well for Indian faces which have a specific complexion varying under certain range. We have taken real life examples and simulated the algorithms in MATLAB successfully. There researcher addressed the problem of automated face recognition by functionally dividing it into face detection and face recognition. Different approaches to the problems of face detection and face recognition were evaluated, and five systems were proposed and implemented using the Matlab technical computing language. In the implemented frontal-view face detection systems, automated face detection was achieved using a deformable template algorithm based on image invariants. The deformable template was implemented with a perceptron. Unsupervised learning using Kohonen Feature Maps was used to create the Perceptron's A-units. The natural symmetry of faces was utilised to improve the efficiency of the face detection model. The deformable template was run down the line of symmetry of the face in search of the exact face location.

Key words: face, detection, recognition, Algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of this effort is to develop new algorithms for a robust pose-invariant face recognition that overcome many of the limitations found in existing facial recognition systems. Specifically, we are interested in addressing the

problem of detecting faces in color images in the presence of various lighting conditions and complex backgrounds as well as recognizing faces under variations in pose, lighting, and expression. This work is separated into two major components (i) Face detection and (ii) Face recognition. Specific tasks include developing modules for face detection, pose estimation, face modeling, face matching, and a user interface.

We have developed a robust, real-time face detection system from color images using a skin-tone color model and facial features. Major facial features are located automatically and color bias is corrected by a lighting compensation technique that automatically estimates the reference white pixels. This technique overcomes the difficulty of detecting the low-luma and high-luma skin tones by applying a nonlinear transform to the color space. We have also developed a robust face detection module to extract faces from cluttered backgrounds in still images. The system is easily extended to work with video image sequences. The proposed system not only detects the face, but also locates important facial features, such as eyes and mouth. These features are crucial to the performance of the face recognition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The project on face recognition had helped the author to have a detailed survey of a number of face recognition algorithms along with their advantages and limitations. Some of the important methods studied will be described in this section. Face recognition systems architecture broadly consists of the three following tasks:

1. Acquisition (Detection, Tracking of face-like images)
2. Feature extraction (Segmentation, alignment & normalization of the face image)
3. Recognition

PROPOSED SYSTEM

We propose a real time face recognition system based on Robust and Mahalanobis distance. The main challenge for a face recognition system is of effective feature extraction. The proposed system utilizes the Eigen face method information reduction for the images. There is an incredible amount of information present even in a small face image. A method must be able to break down pictures so as to effectively represent face images rather than images in general. Base faces are generated and then image being analyzed can be represented by the system as a linear combination of these base faces. Each face that we wish to classify can be projected into face-space and then analyzed as a vector. A k-nearest-neighbor approach, a neural network or even a simple Euclidean distance measure can be used for classification.

The proposed system uses Robust for feature extraction and various distance classifiers such as the Euclidean distance, the Manhattan distance and the Mahalanobis distance.

CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this paper, a new approach to face detection with Gabor wavelets & feed forward neural network is presented. The method uses Gabor wavelet transform & feed forward neural network for both finding feature points and extracting feature vectors. From the experimental results, it is seen that proposed method achieves better results compared to the graph matching and eigenface methods, which are known to be the most successive algorithms. In the proposed algorithm, since the facial features are compared locally, instead of using a general structure, it allows us to make a decision from the parts of the face. For example, when there are sunglasses, the algorithm compares faces in terms of mouth, nose and any other features rather than eyes. Moreover, having a simple matching procedure and low computational cost proposed method is faster than elastic graph matching methods. Proposed method is also robust

to illumination changes as a property of Gabor wavelets, which is the main problem with the eigenface approaches. A new facial image can also be simply added by attaching new feature vectors to reference gallery while such an operation might be quite time consuming for systems that need training.

Although detection performance of the proposed method is satisfactory by any means, in future it would be further improved with some small modifications and/or additional preprocessing of face images. Such improvements can be summarized as;

- 1) A set of weights can be assigned to these feature points by counting the total times of a feature point occurs at those responses.
- 2) When there is a video sequence as the input to the system, a frame giving the “most frontal” pose of a person should be selected to increase the performance of face detection algorithm.
- 3) In order to further speed up the algorithm, number of Gabor filters could be decreased with an acceptable level of decrease in detection performance.

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